

The chemical sensitivity of K β and K α X-ray emission from a systematic investigation of iron compounds

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ABSTRACT: K-fluorescence x-ray emission spectroscopy (XES) is receiving a growing interest in all fields of natural sciences to investigate the local spin. The spin sensitivity in K β (K α) XES stems from the exchange interaction between the unpaired 3*p* (2*p*) and the 3*d* electrons, which is larger for K β than K α . We present a thorough investigation of a large number of iron bearing compounds. The experimental spectra were analyzed in terms of commonly used quantitative parameters (K $\beta_{1,3}$ -first moment, K α_1 -full width at half maximum, and integrated absolute difference –IAD–) and we carefully examined the difference spectra. Multiplet calculations were also performed to elucidate the underlying mechanisms that lead to the chemical sensitivity. Our results confirm a strong influence of covalency on both K β and K α lines. We establish a reliable spin sensitivity of K β XES as it is dominated by the exchange interaction, whose variations can be quantified by either K $\beta_{1,3}$ -first moment or K β -IAD and result in a systematic difference signal lineshape. We find an exception in the K β XES of Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ in water solution, where a new difference spectrum is identified that cannot be reproduced by scaling the exchange integrals. We explain this with strong differences in orbital mixing between the valence orbitals. This result calls for caution in the interpretation of K β XES spectral changes as due to spin variations without careful analysis of the lineshape. For K α XES, the smaller exchange interaction together with the influence of other electron-electron interactions make it difficult to extract a quantity that directly relates to the spin.

INTRODUCTION

X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy was used by Henry Moseley in 1913 to establish the ordering of the elements according to their nuclear charge, which crucially helped to structure the periodic table. It was subsequently discovered that fluorescence lines not only allow for elemental speciation but also show a dependence on the valence shell electron configuration around the X-ray emitting atom.¹ Creation of a hole in the 1*s* shell of a 3*d* transition metal atom, typically by means of photoionization, is followed by emission of the K α (2*p* to 1*s*), K β (3*p* to 1*s*) and valence to 1*s* fluorescence lines. Spectroscopic analysis of the K-fluorescence using an instrument with an energy bandwidth below the lifetime broadening of the 1*s* shell (~ 1 eV) reveals a sensitivity of the spectral shape to the local (*i.e.* around the photo-excited atom) electronic structure. In particular, valence to 1*s* fluorescence lines provide valuable information about the ligand environment^{2–4} while K α and K β lines are very powerful probes of the spin-state.^{5,6} X-ray emission spectroscopy (XES) is used by an increasing number of researchers from all fields of natural sciences for chemical analysis. The renewed interest is triggered by advances in X-ray sources (laboratory X-ray generators and synchrotron radiation) and high-quality wavelength dispersive optics (crystal analyzers) employed in commercial instruments that make XES readily available. The X-rays impinging on the sample do not need to be monochromatic and precisely tunable which makes the combination of XES with diffraction an attractive option. In this context, we also note that experimental artefacts due to sample preparation are less likely to limit the data analysis in X-ray emission than in

absorption spectroscopy.⁷ Experiments at X-ray free electron lasers take advantage of this and employ XES in pump-and-probe studies to investigate ultra-fast processes and to monitor sample integrity.^{8–10} As the number of studies grows and the analysis of more and more complex processes using XES is attempted, a profound understanding of the chemical sensitivity is of paramount importance.

In this work we focus on K α and K β emission lines in 3*d* transition metals. Unlike the valence orbital to 1*s* lines, the core-to-core transitions in K α and K β do not probe the valence shell directly and the chemical sensitivity is thus indirect. The fundamental interactions that shape these emission spectra are well known. Tsutsumi identified intra-atomic interactions between 2*p* (3*p*) and 3*d* unpaired electrons as the strongest mechanism to shape the K α (K β) lines.^{11,12} Atomic multiplet theory is thus the basis to model the spectra. The exchange interaction between the 2*p* (3*p*) and the 3*d* spins provides the K α (K β) lines with sensitivity to the local spin density around the transition metal atom. This gives the possibility of studying locally the spin even in systems without long-range magnetic order. The K α fluorescence yield is 8 times more intense than K β , but the line shape variations due to changes of the spin in the 3*d* shell are stronger in K β and traditionally the latter has been preferred for spin-state studies. K β XES was applied to the study of pressure-,^{13,14} temperature-,¹⁵ doping-,^{16–18} and laser-induced^{19,20} spin-state transitions or to derive the spin evolution in novel Fe-based superconductors.^{21,22} It can be also used to probe the anisotropy of the local spin density by means of angular-dependent measurements as demonstrated in single crystal Mn compounds.²³

The $3p$ - $3d$ exchange interaction splits the $K\beta$ spectrum into low-energy $K\beta'$ and high-energy $K\beta_{1,3}$ features, which can be clearly discerned in high-spin systems and whose energy separation relates to the spin. A quantitative determination of the spin-state evolution from the $K\beta$ emission lines is however not straightforward. Several authors proposed fitting of the spectra to obtain the $K\beta_{1,3}$ - $K\beta'$ energy splitting using three Voigt functions,^{24,25} four Lorentzians²⁶ or even more components.²⁷ Despite of being the dominant mechanism, the $3p$ - $3d$ exchange interaction is not the only one that shapes the $K\beta$ spectra. Multiplet theoretical analysis shows that the exchange splitting cannot be extracted from the separation of the two prominent spectral features. There are mainly two alternative approaches to quantify the spectral variations. One is to extract the first moment position of the $K\beta_{1,3}$ peak,^{28,29} which is assumed to shift with the spin in a linear fashion.⁵ This parameter preserves the sign of the spectral changes which is very important, for example, when following catalytic reactions.^{30,31} The analysis may have a large systematic error as the first moment analysis depends on the chosen energy range around the $K\beta_{1,3}$ line. Alternatively one can follow the evaluation of the integrated absolute difference (IAD), a relative method that was proposed for XES by Vankó et al.³² The change in the spin-state between spectra is obtained by integrating the absolute value of the difference between a given spectrum and a reference spectrum over the whole spectral energy range. Integrating the area in the difference spectra allows identification of small spectral changes as the systematic error is small.

While the interactions that shape the $K\beta$ emission lines are dominated by the $3p$ - $3d$ exchange, the shape of the $K\alpha$ spectra is mainly determined by the $2p$ spin-orbit interaction,^{5,33} which splits the spectrum into two well separated peaks $K\alpha_1$ and $K\alpha_2$ for both high- and low-spin systems. The spin sensitivity is typically found within the $K\alpha_1$ peak,^{12,32,34,35} as $K\alpha_2$ has an extra linewidth due to the $L_2L_3M_{4,5}$ Coster-Kronig decay.^{34,35} A linear relationship between the width of the $K\alpha_1$ peak and the nominal spin as derived from an ionic model was obtained experimentally for cyanides³⁴ and coordination compounds,³² while a deviation from this behavior was reported for some oxides.^{34,36,37}

The magnitude of the intra-atomic exchange interaction ($3p$ - $3d$ or $2p$ - $3d$) depends for a given element on the valence shell spin multiplicity, which, within an ionic picture, is defined by the metal atom oxidation and spin state. This is a very crude description of the electronic structure and the importance of covalency in $K\beta$ ^{5,22,24–27,38–41} and $K\alpha$ ³⁴ spectra has been pointed out by several authors. Experimentally, a reduced $K\beta'$ - $K\beta_{1,3}$ splitting was reported when increasing covalent character in the $K\beta$ spectra of Ni,^{5,41} Mn,^{26,42} and Fe²⁷ compounds having the same nominal spin. The degree of covalency is connected to the magnitude of the exchange interaction as discussed by Glatzel and Bergmann⁵ and recently investigated by Pollock et al. for $K\beta$.²⁷

Most authors agree on the importance of intra-atomic electron-electron interactions but the influence of other contributions is discussed controversially. The creation of a $1s$ vacancy by photoexcitation or particle (electron/ion) impact may lead to several excited states with a $1s$ core hole. Such states may be single (e.g. charge transfer) or double ionized, and the probability of reaching them depends on the mode of core hole creation (photon or particle) and the excitation energy. All those states give rise to K-emission and should thus be considered in calcu-

lations.^{28,43} For $1s$ photoionization the probability of double ionization can be minimized by tuning the incoming photon energy close or below the energy threshold required to excite a second electron, e.g. the KL or KM edge.^{29,44} However, the incident energy still needs to be sufficiently high in order to avoid resonance effects and thus the possibility of multi-ionization processes cannot be fully excluded (see Supporting Information). Furthermore, radiative Auger emission may occur when the $1s$ vacancy is filled.^{45,46} We note that a good agreement between experiment and theory was achieved without considering double ionized states.²⁸ Also, the spectral variations that are observed when the chemical environment of the transition metal atom is changed were successfully modelled in calculations considering only single photoionization processes.²⁷ We thus assume in the present context that multiple ionization processes are sufficiently weak such that they do not influence our conclusions. While this may hold for XES measurements at synchrotron radiation sources, in the case of experiments at X-ray free electron lasers multiple ionized states might contribute considerably.⁴⁷ Finally, the chemical sensitivity in K-emission may also arise from screening effects where the core hole potential is screened less efficiently for higher oxidation states. This change in core hole screening affects $1s$ and $2p/3p$ electrons differently resulting in an energy shift of the K fluorescence lines.^{5,33}

Covalency, multi-electron transitions, and also the final state lifetime broadening^{28,35,48} are difficult to simulate precisely and thus render a full theoretical treatment rather challenging. At the same time, the excellent data quality that nowadays can be achieved allows for a fine analysis of the spectra. With the aim of gaining further insights into the chemical sensitivity in $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ XES beyond an ionic model, we performed a systematic investigation on a wide variety of iron compounds. Iron was chosen because its electron configuration varies around a half-filled d -shell. This helps establishing the spin as the cause of the spectral change rather than other effects (e.g. screening). We measured both $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ spectra on more than 30 iron-containing samples with different oxidation state (+2, +3, +4 and mixed-valence), spin (high-, low- and mixed-spin), ligands (fluorides, sulfides, oxides, etc.), local coordination (octahedral, tetrahedral), and various degrees of metallicity. The experimental results were qualitatively interpreted by means of semi-empirical multiplet simulations. Several systematic $K\beta$ XES studies have previously been reported on different $3d$ transition metal compounds.^{24,25,27,32,38,49} Our study includes a large set of samples measured in the same experimental session and provides a comprehensive overview of the spin sensitivity in not only $K\beta$ but also $K\alpha$ XES.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

XES measurements details. $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ XES spectra were collected at beamline ID26 of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble, France. The storage ring operated in hybrid filling mode with an electron current of 170–200 mA. Three undulators (u35) produced the incoming radiation that was monochromatized by a pair of cryogenically cooled either Si(111) or Si(311) crystals used for the $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ measurements respectively. The photon flux was on the order of 5×10^{13} ph/sec with Si(111) and a factor 5 less with Si(311). The X-rays were focused by two bent Si mirrors to a size of $\approx 600 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$ (horizontal \times vertical) at the sample position. The incident beam absolute energy calibration was performed using a reference metallic iron foil by setting the first inflection

point of the Fe K edge at 7112 eV. Non-resonant K β (7020-7085 eV) and K α (6385-6410 eV) XES spectra were recorded with a step size of 0.2 eV and at an incident energy of 7200 eV. We employed a point-to-point scanning Johann spectrometer. Several Ge crystal analyzers ($R = 1$ m) were arranged with the sample and photon detector in a vertical Rowland geometry. Five Ge(620) and four Ge(440) analyzers were used for the K β (7058 eV, Bragg angle = 79°) and K α (6404 eV, Bragg angle = 75°) emission lines detection respectively.

The angle of the Bragg reflections was not measured precisely and thus an absolute calibration in the emission energy was not performed. The emission spectrometer was aligned using the elastic peak at the K α or K β fluorescence energy. Many authors calibrate the experimental emission energy scales to the values provided by Bearden⁵⁰, a practice we think leads to wrong calibrations. These computed emission line values comprise a significant error (we note that an error as small as 0.1 % in 6000-7000 eV means a considerable error bar of few eV). Furthermore, the tabulated energies in reference 50 for the 3p to 1s decay in 3d transition metals correspond to the center of gravity of the entire K β spectrum but are often wrongly assigned to the K $\beta_{1,3}$ peak maximum intensity.^{24,25,51-53} In our experimental K β spectrum of Fe metal the center of gravity is at 7055.23 eV which is almost 3 eV away from the tabulated value of 7057.98 eV. We believe that the incorrect assignment is due to the fact that, by coincidence, the tabulated value lies very close to the K $\beta_{1,3}$ peak maximum energy position, i.e. errors approximately compensate each other.

A precise absolute energy calibration is elaborate and not required to study chemical sensitivity. A stable relative emission energy calibration is crucial. Consequently, we used slits in front of the sample (700 × 200 μm^2 horizontal x vertical) to define the beam position with respect to the source volume of the emission spectrometer. The slits are placed 550 mm upstream of the sample position and the vertical focusing mirror and monochromator are 17400 mm and 21200 mm upstream of the sample. An upper limit of a possible emission energy scale shift (ΔE) is 14 meV for K β and 17 meV for K α assuming that a vertical movement of the X-ray beam is less than 10 μm . We have determined $\Delta E < 10$ meV between consecutive scans from the measured K β and K α XES spectra in agreement with the expected upper values. The change in source volume between solid and liquid samples does not significantly alter the energy resolution of the XES instrument (see Supporting Information).

The detector was a Si avalanche photodiode (APD) with 200 μm thickness and 10 × 10 mm² active area. In order to assure a linear response of the detector (within a few percent after dead time correction), the count rates in the spectra were kept below 6 × 10⁶ cps by attenuating the incoming beam with Al filters when necessary. The total experimental broadening, determined as the full width at half maximum of the elastic profiles, was 1.4 eV and 0.7 eV for K β and K α measurements where Si(111) and Si(311) monochromator crystals were used respectively. This means an energy bandwidth in the X-ray emission detection of 0.9 eV and 0.7 eV for K β and K α measurements respectively, considering resolving power values of 7000 and 35000 for Si(111) and Si(311) monochromators. X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) measurements at the Fe K edge were also recorded in high-energy-resolution fluorescence detected (HERFD) and total fluorescence yield modes with the main pur-

pose of checking sample quality and evaluating radiation damage effects. All the measurements were performed at room temperature.

Data analysis details. XES spectra were normalized in area using the ranges 7020-7085 eV for K β and 6385-6410 eV for K α . In order to extract quantitative information from the spectral variations across the samples we have evaluated the following parameters commonly used in the analysis of K-emission spectra: K $\beta_{1,3}$ -first moment, K α_1 -full width at half maximum (FWHM), and IAD. For the extraction of K $\beta_{1,3}$ -first moment and K α_1 -FWHM parameters, we have performed a spline interpolation in which the step size was reduced down to 10 meV in both K β and K α spectra. The general definition of the first moment is given by:

$$M_1 = \frac{\sum_j (E_j I_j)}{\sum_j I_j}$$

where E_j and I_j are the energy and intensity of the data point j , respectively. Different choices can be made for the upper and lower limit of the energy range around the K $\beta_{1,3}$ maximum. In order to reduce the systematic error, rather than making a general choice for the energy range we have calculated the first moment including intensities down to 50% of the K $\beta_{1,3}$ maximum in each spectrum. The average of the statistical errors of K $\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 calculated for all the experimental spectra propagating the error of the real counts is only 0.3 meV. We also calculated the first moment using the previous definition applied to the entire measured spectral range for both K β and K α spectra. To differentiate from the first moment of the peak we hereafter refer to this parameter as the center of gravity (COG). Since more than two Lorentzian functions are needed for an accurate curve fitting of the K α XES spectra,⁵⁴ we have alternatively obtained the K α_1 -FWHM from the energy values at 50% of the K α_1 maximum intensity. After comparing the results from various analysis methods, we estimate an uncertainty of ± 0.02 eV in the K α_1 -FWHM values obtained in this way.

The IAD values are defined as:

$$IAD_j = \int_{E_i}^{E_f} |SP_j - SP_{ref}| dE$$

where SP_j is the spectrum j for which the IAD_j value is determined and SP_{ref} the reference spectrum. We have performed the IAD analysis with the spectra normalized in area to unity. The whole spectral range was used for both K β -IAD and K α -IAD. The compound chosen for the reference spectrum (thus with zero IAD value) was K₄Fe(CN)₆·3H₂O where Fe carries no nominal spin. This compound also gives the lowest value of K $\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 (Table 3). The experimental error was estimated by integrating the absolute value of the difference signal between two equivalent spectra and results in 0.003 and 0.002 eV in average for K β and K α spectra respectively.

In order to express the differences between spectra $SP_j - SP_i$ as a percent of the K β or K α XES signal, we have normalized them by the maximum intensity of the corresponding average spectrum $(SP_j + SP_i)/2$. From the real counts N in the measured K β and K α spectra we get N/\sqrt{N} on the order of 10³, which means that spectral variations as small as 0.1 % can be trusted. This has to be compared to the error introduced by the corrected linearity of the detector. This error depends on the differences in count rate between samples and the analysis method. We found that the error in the relative energy calibration (*vide supra*) introduces the dominant error. Since this error is below 10

meV, we have derived the percentage corresponding to the peak-to-peak amplitude in the difference signal between a given spectrum and the same spectrum shifted by this amount. We get a value in the order of 1 % and thus spectral variations down to this value are reliable.

XAS spectra were normalized in area using the full measured energy range, 7100-7200 eV.

Sample details. To illustrate the variety of iron compounds surveyed in this work, we first introduce them in Table 1 grouped into families. A complete list of samples including specific details for each of them (chemical formula, formal valence, nominal spin, information about the origin of the sample with relevant references and quantitative spectral parameters) can be found in Table 3 of the Results and Analysis section. Most of the compounds were synthesized by different providers in which case the expected crystal structure was confirmed by X-ray diffraction measurements. We have purchased from Sigma Aldrich FeS, FeS₂, FeF₂, FeF₃, K₄Fe(CN)₆·3H₂O, K₃Fe(CN)₆, Fe₄[Fe(CN)₆]₃, FeO, Fe₃O₄, α -Fe₂O₃, γ -Fe₂O₃ and FeTiO₃ while the Fe metal foil was supplied by Goodfellow. In this case, sample quality was assessed based on the comparison of the measured XES-XAS spectra with previously reported ones in the literature (XAS spectra of all the compounds can be found in the Supporting Information).

Table 1. List of the compounds studied by K-emission XES grouped into families

Family	Compounds
Sulfides	FeS ₂ , FeS
Cyanides	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ ·3H ₂ O, Fe ₄ [Fe(CN) ₆] ₃ , K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆
Binary oxides	FeO, Fe ₃ O ₄ , α -Fe ₂ O ₃ , γ -Fe ₂ O ₃
Fluorides	FeF ₂ , FeF ₃
Water solutions	[Fe(H ₂ O) ₆] ²⁺ , [Fe(H ₂ O) ₆] ³⁺
Perovskites	SmFeO ₃ , LaFeO ₃ , LaFe _{0.5} Ga _{0.5} O ₃ , La _{0.33} Sr _{0.67} FeO ₃ , Pr _{0.33} Sr _{0.67} FeO ₃ , SrFeO ₃
Double perovskites	Ba ₂ FeReO ₆ , Sr ₂ FeReO ₆ , Ca ₂ FeReO ₆
Spinel	CrFe ₂ O ₄ , MnFe ₂ O ₄ , Co ₂ FeO ₄
Hexagonal ferrites	LuFe ₂ O ₄ , YbFe ₂ O ₄ , YFe ₂ O ₄ , LuFeCoO ₄
Li- or Na-ion based	LiFePO ₄ , β -NaFeO ₂ , Na _{0.7} Mn _{0.5} Fe _{0.5} O ₂
Other oxides	FeTiO ₃
Pnictides	BaFe ₂ As ₂
Iron metal	Fe

All solid samples were prepared in the form of 5 mm diameter pellets with high concentration (90 wt%) except for the air-sensitive compounds (FeS, FeS₂, FeF₂, FeF₃). In this case, the samples were prepared in an inert atmosphere nitrogen-filled glovebag where glass capillaries of 1 mm diameter were filled with powder and then sealed with wax. All solid samples were oriented at 45° relative to the incident beam direction in the horizontal scattering plane. They were all in a polycrystalline form, thus long range order effects are averaged over all the crystallographic directions.⁵⁵ The single crystal of tetragonal BaFe₂As₂ with [001] orientation was the only exception, but

since the sample surface was aligned to 45° with respect to the incident beam direction (that is, 10° off the magic angle⁵⁶), this configuration provides results very close to measurements on a polycrystalline sample.²² The only two liquid samples, [Fe(H₂O)₆]²⁺ and [Fe(H₂O)₆]³⁺, were 0.1 M solutions prepared by dissolving commercial FeSO₄·7H₂O and Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O salts respectively in distilled water at pH = 1^{57,58}. To measure them we used a liquid jet set-up previously described elsewhere.⁵⁹ In this system, a liquid jet of 1 mm diameter is recycled through the X-ray beam, which shines on an uncontained jet part exposed to air.

No sign of radiation damage was observed in any of the samples with the exception of the cyanides and [Fe(H₂O)₆]³⁺. The maximum exposure time without radiation damage effects was determined by performing quick XAS scans (5 seconds total illumination time per scan). For the cyanides, several XES spectra were measured on different sample positions with total exposure time per spectrum below the determined threshold.

Computational details. We have calculated the core-to-core emission using Crispy,⁶⁰ a graphical user interface to the multiplet methods implemented in the Quancy library.⁶¹ We used a two-step approach to calculate the spectra. Starting from all thermally populated states corresponding to the 3dⁿ electronic configuration, we excite one 1s electron into the continuum. The intermediate states formed after photoionization belonging to the 1s¹3dⁿ electronic configuration are then allowed to decay by either a 2p or 3p to 1s dipolar electronic transition. The Hamiltonian used to describe the system includes the atomic multiplet contributions between the 1s, 2p or 3p, and 3d electrons, *i.e.* electron-electron and spin-orbit coupling interactions. The parameters for an isolated Fe²⁺ ion are gathered in Table 2. The electron-electron parameters were all scaled by 0.6 from their Hartree-Fock values, unless stated otherwise. We have also added to the Hamiltonian the contribution of an octahedral crystal field with a 10Dq splitting of either 1.0 eV to have a high-spin electronic configuration or 4.0 eV for a low-spin.

Table 2. Electron-electron (*F* and *G*) and spin-orbit coupling (ζ) multiplet parameters for Fe²⁺

	3d ⁵	1s ¹ 3d ⁵	2p ⁵ 3d ⁵	3p ⁵ 3d ⁵
F_{dd}^2	10.97	12.74	12.82	12.09
F_{dd}^4	6.82	7.57	8.02	7.57
ζ_d	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.06
G_{sd}^2		0.07		
F_{pd}^2			7.45	13.05
G_{pd}^1			5.56	16.17
G_{pd}^3			3.17	9.85
ζ_p			8.20	0.97

A major challenge in calculating the K emission lines is the accurate treatment of the term dependent lifetime broadening. Here we have used an energy dependent broadening to model the decay of the different final states.^{28,48} The energy dependent Lorentzian function used to broaden the calculated K β and K α emission spectra is plotted in Figure S1 of the Supporting Information. In addition, the spectra were convoluted with a 1.2 eV FWHM Lorentzian function to account for the 1s lifetime broadening, and a Gaussian function with a 0.9 eV FWHM for K β spectra or 0.7 eV FWHM for K α spectra to account for the experimental emission energy bandwidths.

THEORY OF X-RAY EMISSION

The main goal of the present study is to correlate modifications in the envelope of the $K\alpha$ and $K\beta$ emission spectra with changes in the spin-state and the chemical environment of the iron center. The apparently simple line shapes result from a complex multiplet structure. The fine structure of the $K\alpha$ and $K\beta$ emission lines is given by the electron-electron (Coulomb and exchange) and spin-orbit coupling interactions within and between the unpaired core and valence electrons. The splitting between the $K\beta_{1,3}$ line and the $K\beta'$ feature is largely determined by the exchange interaction between the $3p$ and $3d$ electrons. For $K\alpha$ emission, the $2p$ spin-orbit coupling is the dominant interaction and splits the spectrum into the $K\alpha_1$ ($2p_{3/2} \rightarrow 1s$) and $K\alpha_2$ ($2p_{1/2} \rightarrow 1s$) peaks, while the exchange interaction between the $2p$ and $3d$ electrons affects mainly their widths and asymmetry. The fact that the $2p$ - $3d$ exchange interaction is weaker than the $2p$ spin-orbit interaction makes the exchange splitting unresolved in the single $K\alpha_1$ and $K\alpha_2$ peaks and thus the spin information more difficult to extract than in $K\beta$. While $K\beta$ spectra can be discussed in LS-coupling scheme, the final states of a $K\alpha$ transition should be discussed in jj -coupling because of the strong $2p$ spin-orbit interaction and thus the spin is not a good quantum number. As follows from multiplet theory, for a zero $3d$ orbital angular momentum ($L = 0$) the $K\alpha_1$ line is broadened by the $2p$ - $3d$ exchange interaction. For $L \neq 0$ the $2p$ - $3d$ direct Coulomb interaction may induce a splitting of similar magnitude.²⁹

Taking the case of the $K\beta$ emission, one can use a simple model to connect the $K\beta_{1,3}$ - $K\beta'$ splitting to the difference in the exchange energy of two electronic states, one having the spin of the $3p$ electron aligned parallel with the spins of the $3d$ valence electrons, the other anti-parallel. Similar arguments can be used to explain the asymmetry of the $K\alpha$ peaks. We would like to emphasise that this approach can come with significant errors as the spectral features cannot always be identified with only those two states. For example, according to the model, complexes having formal spin $S = 0$ should not display any splitting in the $K\beta$ emission lines. However, the presence of a shoulder is clearly visible in the experimental spectra (see Figure 2c). Such features may arise from (direct) Coulomb electron-electron interaction or multi-electron transitions, which are not considered in the model.

The exchange energy of the two states can be calculated as the expectation values of the following spin Hamiltonian:

$$\hat{H}_{exch} = -\frac{1}{2}K_{ij}(1 + 4\hat{S}_i\hat{S}_j)$$

where K_{ij} is the exchange integral between spins i and j belonging to the valence and core subshells, and \hat{S}_i and \hat{S}_j are spin operators. To arrive at the general expression for the exchange energy of an electronic state, we first rewrite the scalar product of the two spin operators as:

$$\hat{S}_i\hat{S}_j = \frac{1}{2}(\hat{S}^2 - \hat{S}_i^2 - \hat{S}_j^2)$$

The expectation value of the operators on the right-hand side is:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle S_i S_j S M_S | \hat{S}^2 - \hat{S}_i^2 - \hat{S}_j^2 | S_i S_j S M_S \rangle \\ = S(S+1) - S_i(S_i+1) - S_j(S_j+1) \end{aligned}$$

where $|S_i S_j S M_S\rangle$ are spin states resulting from the coupling of S_i and S_j to a resultant S and M_S . Using the previous equation, the exchange energy of a spin state can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle S_i S_j S M_S | \hat{H}_{exch} | S_i S_j S M_S \rangle \\ = -\frac{1}{2}K_{ij} \{ 1 \\ + 2[S(S+1) - S_i(S_i+1) - S_j(S_j+1)] \} \end{aligned}$$

The two spin states considered here have total spin $S = S_i - 1/2$ (for anti-parallel alignment) and $S = S_i + 1/2$ (for parallel alignment). The difference energy is then:

$$\Delta E_{exch} = \frac{1}{2}K_{ij}(2S_i+1) - \frac{1}{2}K_{ij}(-2S_i-1) = K_{ij}(2S_i+1)$$

The angular part of the exchange integrals K_{ij} can be calculated analytically, while the radial can be expressed using Slater-Condon parameters (G_{pd}^1 and G_{pd}^3):

$$K_{ij} = mG_{ij}^1 + nG_{ij}^3$$

where m and n are rational numbers that depend on the symmetry of the orbital involved. For the coupling of p and d electrons, after averaging over all possible orbital pairs, we obtain $m = 2/15$ and $n = 21/245$.⁶² The exchange energy difference is then:

$$\Delta E_{exch} = \left(\frac{2}{15}G_{pd}^1 + \frac{21}{245}G_{pd}^3 \right) (2S_d + 1)$$

where S_d represents the spin of the d valence subshell. According to this previous equation, ΔE_{exch} is reduced with decreasing S_d . The exchange splitting depends on the local spin unlike the signal in X-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD) that depends on the spin projection along a specific axis.⁶³ K emission spectroscopy is thus not directly sensitive to the relative alignment between spins on neighboring ions. The dependence on the Slater-Condon parameters (G_{pd}^1 and G_{pd}^3) is less obvious as their evaluation requires knowledge of the radial part of the wavefunctions for the core and valence electrons. Using approximate hydrogenic radial wavefunctions it is straightforward to show that, as the radial functions get more diffused due to a reduction in the effective nuclear charge, the electron-electron exchange integrals become smaller. Therefore, ΔE_{exch} will decrease in cases when the effective nuclear charge of the metal is reduced.

Evaluating ΔE_{exch} using atomic radial wavefunctions has of course its limitations as it does not consider the influence of the surrounding atoms, and therefore it cannot describe spectral variations due to covalency. Two main mechanisms have been used to describe the effects of covalency on electron-electron repulsion parameters.⁶⁴ The first mechanism, termed ‘‘central-field covalency’’, refers to the transfer of negative charge from the ligands to the metal (the metal ion is in fact not as ionic as one would expect from the oxidation state), which reduces the effective nuclear charge of the metal, and results in a decrease of the inter-electronic parameters due to the expansion of the metal orbitals. This mechanism is to be separated from the dilution of the metal orbitals with the ligand orbitals, which is captured in the second mechanism, the ‘‘symmetry-restricted covalency’’. In this case the reduction of the inter-electronic parameters occurs by having more space available for the metal electrons after the formation of the molecular orbitals.

The covalency effects illustrated above can be incorporated into the model in two ways, either by scaling the exchange integrals or by extending the model to include charge transfer electronic configurations. The first approach is straightforward, and it should be sufficient to have a qualitative picture of the covalency effects on the emission spectra. In this case the difference in the exchange energy can be rewritten as:

$$\Delta E_{exch} = \kappa \left(\frac{2}{15} G_{pd}^1 + \frac{21}{245} G_{pd}^3 \right) (2S_d + 1)$$

where κ is the factor used to scale the integrals.

Multiplet calculations have been used extensively to study the effects of electronic interactions on the shape of the emission lines.^{5,27,35,38} In the following we provide a systematic study of covalency effects on both $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ emission spectra for high-spin (HS) and low-spin (LS) Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions (see Figure 1). Due to the semi-empirical nature of the calculations, it is simple to separate the different contributions to the spectral shape. Scaling the exchange integrals G_{pd}^1 and G_{pd}^3 has a significant influence on the calculated spectra. In the case of $K\beta$, reducing the scale factor results in smaller $K\beta_{1,3}$ - $K\beta'$ splitting, in line with the analytical model presented above. The changes in the $K\alpha$ emission are less significant and are mostly limited to changes in the asymmetry of the lines. This can be understood if we consider that the exchange integrals of the $2p$ - $3d$ electrons are about a third of the values of the $3p$ - $3d$ electrons (refer to Table 2), and therefore for the same scale factor the spectral variations will span a smaller energy range in the former case. Similar results are found in the calculated spectra for HS and LS Fe^{3+} ions (Figure S2 in the Supporting Information).

Figure 1. Calculated spectra showing the effect of scaling the exchange integrals G_{pd}^1 and G_{pd}^3 on the Fe $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ XES spectra of the Fe^{2+} HS (a, b) and LS (c, d) ions.

Scaling the F_{pd}^2 Coulomb electron-electron integrals has a significantly smaller impact on both $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ spectra (see Figure S3 in the Supporting Information). Varying the 10Dq crystal field splitting results in the expected HS to LS transition that is accompanied by significant differences in the spectral shapes (see Figure S4 in the Supporting Information); the changes between the spectra corresponding to the same spin-state are however minimal in agreement with previous

works.^{27,35} While multiplet calculations can be useful in gauging the effects of the different interactions on the spectral shapes, they should be used with caution when making more quantitative predictions. Their parameterized nature and also the approximate treatment of the final state lifetime broadening are limiting factors for more quantitative considerations.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section is organized as follows: First, we quantify the $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ spectra using different methods and compare the results. We then discuss to what extent simple models that allow consideration of covalency can explain the observed trends. Finally, we compare differences of pairs of $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ spectra. The peculiar behavior of Fe ions dissolved in water leads us to the identification of a mechanism for chemical sensitivity beyond intra-atomic exchange interaction.

$K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ XES spectra. We present the experimental spectra comparing compounds with the same formal valence and nominal spin divided into HS and LS. Figure 2 shows the $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ XES spectra of all the Fe^{2+} samples. The spectra of the Fe^{3+} and mixed-valence samples can be found in the Supporting Information. The values of the extracted spectral parameters for each compound can be found in Table 3. Spectral variations are observed in both $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ XES not only between the groups of HS and LS systems but also within each group. The nominal spin-state is derived from the formal oxidation state within an ionic picture and considering the crystal field splitting. The spectral variations for identical formal spin and oxidation states must thus be explained by covalency.

Figure 2. Fe $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ XES spectra of the Fe^{2+} HS (a, b) and LS (c, d) compounds recorded at an incident energy of 7200 eV.

Table 3. Chemical formula, formal valence, nominal spin, origin of the sample together with relevant references and quantitative spectral parameters of each of the compounds studied by K-emission XES

Compound	Formal valence	Nominal spin*	Origin & references	K $\beta_{1,3}$ -M $_1$ (eV)	K β -IAD	K β -COG (eV)	K α_1 -FWHM (eV)	K α -IAD	K α -COG (eV)
Fe	0	1	a & ^{65,66}	7058.91	0.284(3)	7055.13	2.77(2)	0.257(2)	6399.52
FeS ₂	+2	0	a & ⁶⁷	7058.36	0.148(3)	7055.14	2.26(2)	0.229(2)	6399.54
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ ·3H ₂ O	+2	0	a & ^{49,68}	7057.94	0	7055.21	2.06(2)	0	6399.32
FeS	+2	2	a & ⁶⁷	7059.00	0.326(3)	7055.14	3.27(2)	0.318(2)	6399.65
FeO	+2	2	a & ⁶⁹⁻⁷¹	7059.39	0.419(3)	7055.04	3.66(2)	0.331(2)	6399.56
FeTiO ₃	+2	2	a & ^{72,73}	7059.72	0.491(3)	7055.29	3.76(2)	0.331(2)	6399.53
BaFe ₂ As ₂	+2	2	d & ²²	7058.76	0.243(3)	7055.16	2.74(2)	0.286(2)	6399.61
LiFePO ₄	+2	2	c & ⁷⁴	7059.72	0.501(3)	7055.27	3.75(2)	0.347(2)	6399.56
FeF ₂	+2	2	a & ⁶⁸	7060.03	0.575(3)	7055.34	-	-	-
[Fe(H ₂ O) ₆] ²⁺	+2	2	a & ^{57,58}	7060.11	0.559(3)	7055.45	-	-	-
LuFe ₂ O ₄	+2.5	2.25	b & ⁷⁵	7059.59	0.454(3)	7055.20	3.63(2)	0.310(2)	6399.48
YbFe ₂ O ₄	+2.5	2.25	b & ⁷⁵	7059.51	0.451(3)	7055.20	3.65(2)	0.314(2)	6399.49
YFe ₂ O ₄	+2.5	2.25	b & ⁷⁵	7059.51	0.450(3)	7055.20	3.64(2)	0.310(2)	6399.48
CrFe ₂ O ₄	+2.5	2.25	b & ⁷⁶	7059.42	0.429(3)	7055.20	3.60(2)	0.314(2)	6399.52
Fe ₄ [Fe(CN) ₆] ₃	+2.57	1.43	a & ⁷⁷	7058.80	0.285(3)	7055.20	2.99(2)	0.172(2)	6399.35
Fe ₃ O ₄	+2.67	2.33	b & ^{69,71}	7059.58	0.449(3)	7055.13	3.52(2)	0.301(2)	6399.50
Sr ₂ FeReO ₆	+2.7	2.35	b & ⁷⁸	7059.61	0.476(3)	7055.20	3.52(2)	0.305(2)	6399.49
Ba ₂ FeReO ₆	+2.75	2.375	b & ⁷⁹	7059.60	0.465(3)	7055.22	3.51(2)	0.297(2)	6399.46
Ca ₂ FeReO ₆	+2.8	2.4	b & ⁷⁸	7059.59	0.461(3)	7055.16	3.48(2)	0.293(2)	6399.46
K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	+3	0.5	a & ^{49,68}	7058.44	0.152(3)	7055.23	2.60(2)	0.117(2)	6399.26
α -Fe ₂ O ₃	+3	2.5	a & ^{69,71}	7059.67	0.467(3)	7055.14	3.49(2)	0.301(2)	6399.48
γ -Fe ₂ O ₃	+3	2.5	a & ^{69,71}	7059.59	0.458(3)	7055.15	3.51(2)	0.299(2)	6399.53
LuFeCoO ₄	+3	2.5	b & ⁷⁵	7059.60	0.462(3)	7055.21	3.56(2)	0.299(2)	6399.46
MnFe ₂ O ₄	+3	2.5	b & ^{73,80}	7059.59	0.465(3)	7055.24	3.57(2)	0.305(2)	6399.45
Co ₂ FeO ₄	+3	2.5	b & ⁸¹	7059.57	0.450(3)	7055.20	3.55(2)	0.299(2)	6399.46
SmFeO ₃	+3	2.5	b & ⁸²	7059.61	0.477(3)	7055.12	3.47(2)	0.290(2)	6399.46
LaFeO ₃	+3	2.5	b & ^{73,83}	7059.61	0.472(3)	7055.15	3.48(2)	0.286(2)	6399.45
LaFe _{0.5} Ga _{0.5} O ₃	+3	2.5	b & ⁸³	7059.70	0.486(3)	7055.14	3.50(2)	0.290(2)	6399.43
β -NaFeO ₂	+3	2.5	c & ⁸⁴	7059.50	0.432(3)	7055.12	3.49(2)	0.290(2)	6399.43
Na _{0.7} Mn _{0.5} Fe _{0.5} O ₂	+3	2.5	c & ⁸⁵	7059.70	0.490(3)	7055.22	3.58(2)	0.294(2)	6399.44
FeF ₃	+3	2.5	a & ^{27,68}	7060.29	0.617(3)	7055.37	-	-	-
[Fe(H ₂ O) ₆] ³⁺	+3	2.5	a & ^{57,58}	7059.90	0.540(3)	7055.35	-	-	-
La _{0.33} Sr _{0.67} FeO ₃	+3.67	2.17	b & ^{86,87}	7059.65	0.440(3)	7055.11	3.43(2)	0.265(2)	6399.38
Pr _{0.33} Sr _{0.67} FeO ₃	+3.67	2.17	b & ⁸⁷	7059.65	0.440(3)	7055.12	3.44(2)	0.261(2)	6399.37
SrFeO ₃	+4	2	b & ^{73,86}	7059.51	0.429(3)	7055.13	3.36(2)	0.258(2)	6399.39

a, b, c, and d refer to commercial samples and provided by Dr. J. Blasco, Dr. D. Baster, and Dr. F. Hardy respectively. Errors due to the uncertainty in the relative energy calibration are on the order of ± 0.01 eV (statistical errors are negligible within this value).

*Nominal spin (S) values are as derived from an ionic model taking into consideration the formal valence and the crystal field splitting. For the monovalent samples, this yields for Fe²⁺ ($3d^6$) either $S = 0$ (low-spin) or $S = 2$ (high-spin), for Fe³⁺ ($3d^5$) either $S = 0.5$ (low-spin) or $S = 2.5$ (high-spin) and for Fe⁴⁺ ($3d^4$) $S = 2$ (high-spin). For the mixed-valence samples, the non-integer average valence is deduced based on the site(s) occupation in terms of formal integer valences and normalized by the number of iron atoms in the chemical formula. The nominal spin is then calculated assigning the corresponding S value to each integer valence. For example, in Fe₃O₄ there are two sites where one is shared such that the formal valence is given by $1/3[1 \times \text{Fe}^{3+} + 2 \times (1/2 \text{Fe}^{2+} + 1/2 \text{Fe}^{3+})]$ and hence the nominal spin by $1/3[1 \times S = 2.5 + 2 \times (1/2 S = 2 + 1/2 S = 2.5)]$. For Fe metal (zero formal valence), the experimental spin moment value is taken as the nominal spin.

$K\beta$ fluorescence is dominated by the $3p$ - $3d$ exchange interaction whose magnitude relates to the spin density around the X-ray emitting metal atom. An analysis of the spectral shape may thus provide the local spin if one is able to extract a spectral quantity solely influenced by the exchange interaction. We have first verified the nominal spin dependence of the $K\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 parameter in Figure 3. On average the $K\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 increases with the nominal spin. However, a significant spread is obtained for compounds with the same nominal spin value.

Figure 3. $K\beta_{1,3}$ -first moments as a function of the nominal spin. The data are shown grouped into families of compounds as described in Table 1.

Another parameter commonly used to quantify the spin in $K\beta$ emission is the IAD (Figure S7 in the Supporting Information shows the $K\beta$ -IADs values versus the nominal spin). We have quantified the correlation between $K\beta$ -IAD and $K\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 through the Pearson correlation coefficient r as shown in Figure 4. An excellent correlation exists between the two computed $K\beta$ -parameters ($r > 0.99$) which confirms that both of them reflect in the same way the magnitude of the $3p$ - $3d$ exchange interaction and thus provide the same spin sensitivity.

Although the $2p$ spin-orbit coupling is the strongest interaction in $K\alpha$ fluorescence, the $2p$ - $3d$ exchange interaction also shapes the spectrum and we have evaluated the spin sensitivity by analyzing the correlation between the most widely used $K\alpha$ -parameters and $K\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 . The correlation plots of both $K\alpha_1$ -FWHM and $K\alpha$ -IAD with $K\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 are also shown in Figure 4 (Figure S8 and Figure S9 in the Supporting Information show the evolution of both parameters versus nominal spin). We get a lower degree of correlation between $K\alpha_1$ -FWHM and $K\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 ($r \sim 0.95$) and yet a much lower degree for $K\alpha$ -IAD ($r \sim 0.81$). This means that, with respect to the $K\beta$ parameters, $K\alpha_1$ -FWHM and especially $K\alpha$ -IAD contain additional contributions. Compared with the other spectral indicators, the large $K\alpha$ -IADs in the more covalent samples (sulfides, pnictides, and iron metal) are due to the very intense $K\alpha_1$ peaks shown by these compounds. In addition, a close inspection of the experimental $K\alpha$ spectra reveals systematic intensity variations in the $K\alpha_1$ peak satellite at about 6400 eV (see Figure 2b and Figure 2d). It appears that for the Fe^{2+} HS samples, the more covalent the compound, the weaker the satellite. The opposite behavior is obtained for the LS samples. These intensity variations in the $K\alpha_1$ peak are well captured in the multiplet calculations when the exchange integral is rescaled for HS compounds only (see Figure 1b and Figure 1d).

Figure 4. Correlation graphs for $K\beta$ -IADs, $K\alpha_1$ -FWHMs and $K\alpha$ -IADs with $K\beta_{1,3}$ -first moments. The data are shown grouped into families of compounds as described in Table 1. The computed Pearson correlation coefficient (r) for each pair is indicated. The dashed lines show the linear regression.

Chemical dependence of the center of gravity. We have also extracted the values of the center of gravity (COG) of the spectra (Table 3). Neither $K\beta$ -COG nor $K\alpha$ -COG reveal any systematic chemical dependence on the oxidation state. Thus, variations in core hole screening due to different valence shell populations are not detectable. Going beyond an ionic model one may assume that for the more covalent compounds the Fe is less ionic and thus more charge in the valence band contributes to the screening reducing the effective nuclear potential experienced by the $3p$ or $2p$ electrons.⁸⁸ However, we have not found a clear correlation of higher values of either $K\beta$ -COG or

$K\alpha$ -COG with increasing average ligand electronegativity (Figure S10 in the Supporting Information). It seems that the Fe charge density that contributes to the core hole screening varies only very little among all compounds despite the existing variations in the local spin. As previously done by other authors,^{32,37} we also performed the IAD analysis of the $K\beta$ spectra after the COG alignment in order to get values without the influence of the screening effects (Figure S11 in the Supporting Information). However, the COG alignment has very little effect on the $K\beta$ -IAD parameter.

Covalency. We have investigated the influence of covalence variations due to different ligands on the exchange interaction. The covalency of a compound relates to the ligand electronegativity. Bocquet et al.⁸⁹ showed that, for a given cation, modifying the ligand results in a change of the charge transfer energy Δ ; the more electronegative the ligand, the larger is Δ . With increasing ligand electronegativity, the ligand p bands (orbitals) are lowered with respect to the metal $3d$ bands (orbitals) increasing the energy required for an electron to be transferred to the metal ion. Figure 5 shows the evolution of the $K\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 parameter as a function of the average ligand electronegativity focusing on the monovalent Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} samples. The average ligand electronegativity of each compound was calculated using the values in ref 90. We note that this analysis has its limitations as it only takes into account the ligand identity. A more comprehensive analysis would consider the orbitals that take part in the bond between metal ion and ligand.

Figure 5. $K\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 parameter as a function of the average ligand electronegativity for the (a) Fe^{2+} and (b) Fe^{3+} samples. Filled and empty symbols differentiate between HS and LS compounds respectively. For clarity, the chemical formula of the compound associated to each data point is also indicated.

$K\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 shows a positive correlation with the ligand electronegativity for the Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} HS solid state samples, which means that the higher the ligand electronegativity, the larger the exchange interaction and hence the local spin. An exception are the Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions dissolved in H_2O showing that this approach might have limitations (*vide infra*). Conversely, for the Fe^{2+} LS compounds (FeS and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$) an inverse relationship is obtained. This finding can be explained thinking in a configuration interaction picture in which the ground state is expressed as a linear combination of $3d^n$ and $3d^{n+1}\underline{L}$ (ligand hole) configurations, where the charge transfer energy Δ determines how much of the second configuration is admixed. The ground state of Fe^{2+} can be expressed as a linear combination of $3d^6$ and $3d^7\underline{L}$ configurations, which have formal spin $S = 2$ and $S = 3/2$ respectively in the HS case and $S = 0$ and $S = 1/2$ in the LS case (refer to Figure S12 in the Supporting Information). A decrease in electronegativity (i.e. decrease in Δ), means that the $3d^7\underline{L}$ configuration contributes more, which reduces the net spin in the HS case but increases the total spin for LS. These observations support the assumption that $K\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 is a good quantity to study the local spin density. The spread that we observe for identical ligands shows that other parameters such as local geometry (bond distances and angles, coordination number) are also important as they will influence the spin density.

The effect of the local symmetry can also be explained by covalency changes. We compare in Figure S13 of the Supporting Information the data of β - $NaFeO_2$ and $Na_{0.7}Mn_{0.5}Fe_{0.5}O_2$, both Fe^{3+} HS compounds but with tetrahedral (T_d)⁸⁴ and octahedral (O_h)⁸⁵ local coordination of the Fe ion, respectively. The spectral differences agree with a more covalent character in the sample with Fe in T_d symmetry (note also the smaller $K\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 value in β - $NaFeO_2$ compared with $Na_{0.7}Mn_{0.5}Fe_{0.5}O_2$ in Figure 5b). Absence of inversion symmetry in T_d coordination enhances orbital mixing. Looking at the character table for the T_d point group we note that Fe p and some d orbitals have T_2 symmetry as do some molecular orbitals formed by ligand s and p orbitals. This means a stronger mixing between ligand metal orbitals compared with O_h symmetry. Another argument in favor of the T_d coordination being more covalent than O_h is the shorter bond distance in the former. In Figure S13 are also illustrated the T_d ($e^2t_2^3$) and O_h ($t_2g^3e_g^2$) coordination diagrams of Fe^{3+} in HS configuration. For T_d coordination, there are more unpaired electrons in the outer t_2 orbital which has more covalent character compared with the e orbitals as it is less strongly bound. The situation is reversed for the O_h coordination case. The same evolution in $K\beta$ spectra between O_h and T_d coordination was reported by Peng et al.³⁸ for Mn^{2+} ($3d^5$ configuration) compounds and also by Gamblin et al.²⁴ for Co^{2+} ($3d^7$ configuration) samples.

A metallic compound can be viewed as an extremely covalent case. We show in Figure S14 of the Supporting Information the $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ XES spectra of iron metal together with the samples with more metallic behavior among the measured compounds (the sulfides and the pnictide $BaFe_2As_2$). The $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ XES spectra of iron metal agree with previously reported ones.^{34,37,91} For metallic systems, the $K\beta$ spectrum is characterized by a very broad $K\beta'$ shoulder while the $K\alpha$ features are narrow with an intense $K\alpha_1$ peak as earlier recorded for various $3d$ transition metals.⁹¹

We have also examined the effect of a change in covalency due to an increase in the nominal valence. Figure S15 of the Supporting Information shows the evolution of $K\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 as a

function of the formal oxidation state for all the measured compounds with the exception of the mixed-spin system $\text{Fe}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_3$. In a purely ionic model and considering the crystal field splitting, when going from Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} (and keeping the same spin-state, either HS or LS) the nominal spin increases, and one would expect an increase in the exchange interaction. This behavior is indeed observed for the fluorides, binary oxides and cyanides. However, the water solutions show an unexpected opposite behavior (we elaborate more on this later on in a dedicated section). In the family of simple perovskites, we observe a decrease of the $\text{K}\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 parameter as expected from the nominal spin evolution when going from Fe^{3+} to Fe^{4+} (HS) samples.

Difference signals. $\text{K}\beta$ and $\text{K}\alpha$ XES spectroscopy is often used to detect the evolution of a sample as a function of, e.g. doping or external excitation, and the results are shown as spectral differences. We present in the following an analysis of the difference spectra due to variations in nominal spin (ΔS). For that, in the collection of differences presented in Figure 6 we distinguish between two groups of signals: $\Delta S > 0$ and $\Delta S = 0$. For the $\Delta S = 0$ group we have performed the differences such that they yield a positive variation of $\text{K}\beta_{1,3}$ - M_1 . In all cases, the difference spectra are expressed in % with respect to the maximum intensity of the corresponding average. This allows a direct comparison of the amplitudes in the difference signals between $\text{K}\beta$ and $\text{K}\alpha$. A more extended collection of difference signals showing also the original spectra and a table including the peak-to-peak amplitudes are provided in the Supporting Information.

Figure 6. Selection of Fe $\text{K}\beta$ (a, c) and $\text{K}\alpha$ (b, d) XES difference spectra for positive variations in nominal spin ($\Delta S > 0$) (a, b) and nominally zero variations in nominal spin ($\Delta S = 0$) (c, d).

The $\text{K}\beta$ difference spectra for $\Delta S > 0$ and also $\Delta S = 0$ show a systematic down-up feature at the $\text{K}\beta_{1,3}$ peak energy when going from low to high energy. This is a result of the reduction in the exchange splitting. Along with this, a smaller intensity up-

down feature appears at the $\text{K}\beta'$ shoulder energy. We note that the latter is clearly discerned when HS spectra are involved in the difference signal (e.g. $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{FeO}$ or $\text{FeF}_2 - \text{FeO}$), while it shifts to higher energies and merges with the main feature around the $\text{K}\beta_{1,3}$ peak when at least one LS spectrum is involved. This is the case of $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 - \text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{FeS}_2 - \text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and to a lesser extent of $\text{FeS} - \text{FeS}_2$.

The $\text{K}\alpha$ difference spectra show a more complex behavior. In the group of $\Delta S > 0$ differences, sulfides and cyanides follow each other in the $\text{K}\alpha_1$ peak energy while they go in reverse directions at the $\text{K}\alpha_2$ energy. The binary oxides show a broader positive structure below 6405 eV and a negative signal above this energy, with opposite sign compared with the sulfide and cyanide pairs. The $\Delta S = 0$ difference $\text{FeS}_2 - \text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows a down-up feature around 6405 eV in agreement with sulfides and cyanides in the $\Delta S > 0$ group. The different signs that we have obtained for the binary oxides could be then due to the fact that they result from the difference of two HS compounds. The difference $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_2 - \beta\text{-NaFeO}_2$, both HS samples, agrees with this observation.

The peak-to-peak amplitude in the $\Delta S > 0$ differences is in general larger for $\text{K}\beta$ than for $\text{K}\alpha$. The smaller chemical sensitivity of the $\text{K}\alpha$ lines compared to $\text{K}\beta$ is explained by the weaker $2p$ - $3d$ exchange interaction (a factor of 3 less for a $3d^6$ system cf. Table 2). This is important for experimental considerations as the smaller spectral difference may reduce the advantage of the higher fluorescence intensity of the $\text{K}\alpha$ lines. The dependence is quadratic: the detection of a spectral difference that is smaller by a factor of 2, requires 4 times longer counting times.⁹² We also note the different amplitudes within both $\text{K}\beta$ and $\text{K}\alpha$ groups for the same nominal spin variation $\Delta S = 0.5$, for example in the case of cyanides, oxides, and fluorides (see Table S1 in the Supporting Information). Interestingly, a change in covalency due to different ligand electronegativity ($\text{FeF}_2 - \text{FeO}$) may result in a stronger spectral difference than a change in oxidation state ($\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{FeO}$). Our results also show one case in the group of $\Delta S = 0$ differences where the amplitude is considerably larger for $\text{K}\alpha$ compared to $\text{K}\beta$ ($\text{FeS}_2 - \text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$).

We have pointed out previously that multiplet calculations should be used with care for quantitative predictions. While the trends are correctly captured, various discrepancies can be observed between theory and experiment for the individual spectra. This is expected as in the present study the parameters of the calculations are not optimized on a case-by-case basis. For the difference spectra, these discrepancies can result in contrasting spectral features between theory and experiment. As can be seen in Figure 7, calculations accurately capture the shape of the measured $\text{K}\beta$ difference spectra without further adjustments of the parameters used to examine the trends presented in the previous section. On the other hand, for $\text{K}\alpha$ the theoretical difference signal involving the HS and LS spectra shows an inverted $\text{K}\alpha_1$ feature when compared with experiment (blue lines in Figure 6b and Figure 7b). The dissimilarities are even more pronounced when comparing the difference signal of compounds with different oxidation states (green lines in Figure 6b and Figure 7b).

Figure 7. Calculated Fe K β (a) and K α (b) XES difference spectra.

The particular case of the water solutions. The K β XES data of the pair of water solution samples yields a new type of difference signal, which deserves further discussion. In Figure 8 we show the $\Delta S > 0$ differences when going from Fe $^{3+}$ to Fe $^{2+}$ for both water solutions and fluorides as well as the original spectra. While for the fluorides we observe the typical difference signal, for the water solutions the main feature shows an unexpected opposite sign. The fact that, in the difference spectrum of the water solutions both features at the K β' and K $\beta_{1,3}$ energies exhibit the same sign, means that the signal cannot be reproduced by scaling the exchange integrals. We also note that the K $\beta_{1,3}$ -M $_1$ parameter for Fe in solution follows the opposite trend than expected from the ground state spin multiplicity (see Figure 3).

Figure 8. Fe K β XES of (a) water solutions and (b) fluorides and the corresponding Fe $^{3+}$ - Fe $^{2+}$ difference signals (c) and (d) respectively. Detail of the pre-edge region of the HERFD-XAS spectra measured at the K $\beta_{1,3}$ emission line of (e) water solutions and (f) fluorides.

This seems to be at odds with an analysis of the K pre-edge XAS spectra of the compounds (Figure 8) where line shapes are found that are typical for an iron oxidation and spin state.⁶⁸ The K pre-edges directly probe the low energy unoccupied orbitals and are mainly shaped by the crystal field splitting and electron-electron interactions within the 3d manifold. The pre-edge spectral shape reflects the ground state spectroscopic term (6A_1 for Fe $^{3+}$ and 5T_2 for Fe $^{2+}$), while the XES lines probe occupied orbitals and are indirectly sensitive to the local spin via the exchange interaction. The K pre-edges show the expected spectral shape and energy position for Fe $^{2+}$ and Fe $^{3+}$ in solution in agreement with the fluorides. A closer inspection of the relative intensities in the two pre-edge features of [Fe(H $_2$ O) $_6$] $^{3+}$ reveals however a significant deviation from the expected 3:2 intensity ratio for the crystal field split t_{2g} and e_g orbitals in O $_h$ symmetry. A similar observation was made for α -Fe $_2$ O $_3$ and was found to arise from a strong p - d mixing owing to a distortion of the FeO $_6$ octahedra.⁹³ The ferric ($S = 2.5$) water solution species is more covalent than the ferrous ($S = 2.0$), which leads to a smaller value of K $\beta_{1,3}$ -M $_1$ in the former (*cf.* Figure 3). In agreement with this result, the K β difference signals between fluoride and water solution samples for the Fe $^{2+}$ and Fe $^{3+}$ pairs suggest a similar iconicity in the ferrous samples while they agree with a stronger covalent character in [Fe(H $_2$ O) $_6$] $^{3+}$ than in FeF $_3$ (see Figures S30 and S31 in the Supporting Information).

Therefore, the results from both spectroscopies K β XES and K pre-edge XAS are consistent and even complementary. The new type of K β XES difference signal found for the water solutions may be explained as due to strong differences in p - d mixing between the samples, which dominate over the expected change following the nominal spin. The K pre-edge shows that the crystal field split 3d orbitals have different degrees of p - d mixing.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Our survey on the K β and K α XES spectra of a large variety of Fe-based compounds with different oxidation state, spin, ligands, and local coordination has revealed key information regarding the chemical dependence. The K β spectrum is most strongly shaped by the valence shell spin state as the exchange integrals are significantly larger than any other interaction terms. We thus started with the assumption that the spectral indicators extracted from the K β lines are closely related to the spin density around Fe. The aim of the analysis of the K α lines was to assess to what extent these lines could be used for retrieving spin information, as they are more intense and sharper, so experimentally they are an attractive alternative.

The experimental spectra exhibit important variations in both emission line shapes beyond the nominal spin state. The quantitative analysis of the local spin in terms of various parameters commonly used in K β and K α XES (K $\beta_{1,3}$ -M $_1$, K β -IAD, K α_1 -FWHM and K α -IAD), gives a continuous distribution of values which we rationalize by invoking covalency. We obtained a high degree of correlation between K $\beta_{1,3}$ -M $_1$ and K β -IAD which demonstrates that both of them are good indicators of the exchange interaction. In general, for a given nominal spin value, an increase in covalency decreases the exchange interaction and so do the parameters. Interestingly, we have found among our measured samples some cases for which the situation is reversed. In particular, for Fe $^{2+}$ LS samples the exchange interaction increases upon an increase in covalency as opposed to Fe $^{2+}$ and Fe $^{3+}$ HS compounds. This can be understood by considering

ligand-to-metal charge transfer where the ground state is expressed as a linear combination of $3d^n$ and $3d^{n+1}\underline{L}$ (ligand hole) configurations. The second configuration may either increase or decrease the total spin depending on the d count and the spin-state (HS or LS). We have also evaluated the correlation of the extracted $K\alpha$ parameters with $K\beta_{1,3}\text{-}M_1$. Compared with the excellent degree of correlation between the two $K\beta$ spectral indicators, $K\alpha_1\text{-FWHM}$ shows a lower correlation. A previous work in Mn perovskites⁹⁴ also reported a slightly different evolution between $K\alpha_1\text{-FWHM}$ and $K\beta\text{-IAD}$ parameters. Our results for $K\alpha\text{-IAD}$ show that this parameter is even more poorly correlated with $K\beta_{1,3}\text{-}M_1$. The reason for the discrepancy between the two $K\alpha$ spectral indicators is that the intense $K\alpha_1$ peak in the more covalent samples results in larger IAD values. A recent pump-and-probe study in a photo-switchable Fe molecule where $K\alpha$ and $K\beta$ XES were recorded simultaneously, also found different behaviors of $K\alpha_1\text{-IAD}$ and $K\beta\text{-IAD}$ parameters.⁹⁵

The influence of screening effects in $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ was also evaluated by obtaining the COG of each spectrum. The lack of a clear trend between our $K\beta\text{-COG}$ and $K\alpha\text{-COG}$ values and the oxidation state or ligand electronegativity makes us conclude that the screening effects must be very small, and the spectra are mainly dominated by electron-electron interactions. This finding suggests that the observed local spin density modifications as a function of the ligand electronegativity do not modify significantly the charge density.

While in many applications the relative change of the spin is sufficient information, the possibility of an absolute determination of the local spin would be very attractive. This requires two assumptions: 1) $K\beta_{1,3}\text{-}M_1$ provides a quantity that is proportional to the spin and 2) the spin is known for two compounds. We use the nominal spin of those compounds with lowest ($K_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and highest (FeF_3) value of $K\beta_{1,3}\text{-}M_1$ (refer to Table 3) as calibration points and determine the spin values for all other compounds by applying a linear regression. This procedure raises many questions. Most importantly one may ask whether it is reasonable to assign a spin to a single atom in a compound. The Coulomb interaction together with the radial distribution of the of the $2p/3p$ orbitals defines how “local” the K emission probe is. As several mechanisms may modify the exchange interaction, there is no simple functional relation between $K\beta_{1,3}\text{-}M_1$ and the spin. Using $K\beta_{1,3}\text{-}M_1$ and assuming a linear relation is thus a definition rather than a measurement of the local spin. Good qualitative agreement with theory has been achieved previously.¹⁷

Figure 9 shows the nominal spin values versus $K\beta_{1,3}\text{-}M_1$ and versus calibrated spin values. The calibration curve divides the figure into two halves where the upper (lower) part contains the data points with calibrated values lower (higher) than the nominal spin. The derived spin values from such a calibration lead in general to values lower than the nominal spin due to bonding. In the case of the Fe^{2+} LS cyanide FeS_2 , covalency increases the total spin as previously discussed and the calibrated value is higher than the nominal spin. We note that the calibrated values for HS FeF_2 and $[\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$ samples appear slightly larger than their nominal spin. One may choose to use the fluorides as calibrants for the linear regression which would lead to considerably higher spin values for all other compounds. Interestingly, the calibrated value for metallic iron is in very good agreement with the experimental spin magnetic moment.^{65,66}

Figure 9. Nominal spin values versus $K\beta_{1,3}\text{-}M_1$ (top x-axis) and calibrated spin values (bottom x-axis) as detailed in the text. The data are shown grouped into families of compounds as described in Table 1. The dashed lines indicate the calibration curve used.

Ideally, our study could be further supported by density functional theory (DFT) calculations. In this way, one could obtain the population analysis in order to calculate theoretical effective spin values and compare them with the experimental results, as it was done in previous studies.^{17,25,27} Rather than performing a calibration based on nominal spin values for the measured model compounds which was also done in earlier works,^{15–18,21} more realistic results should be obtained if effective spin values are used instead as suggested in ref 6.

We have obtained additional insights into the chemical information contained in $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ emission by looking at the fine structure in the difference spectra from selected pairs of compounds. For the $K\beta$ lines, the difference signal shows a systematic line shape and arises from changes in the $3p\text{-}3d$ exchange interaction that can be quantified in either $K\beta_{1,3}\text{-}M_1$ or $K\beta\text{-IAD}$ parameters. This demonstrates that $K\beta$ XES is a reliable probe of the local spin. However, we have encountered an exception in the $K\beta$ XES data of the Fe ions in water solution. The $K\beta_{1,3}\text{-}M_1$ parameter of Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} in solution follows the opposite trend than expected from the ground state spin multiplicity, and the difference signal shows a new type of lineshape that cannot be reproduced by scaling the exchange integrals. Inspection of the K pre-edge XAS data reveals that the e_g orbitals from the $3d$ manifold are strongly affected by $p\text{-}d$ mixing in Fe^{3+} in solution, which we speculate could be the reason for the unexpected behavior in the $K\beta$ XES data. This finding has important implications as it is the first example of a $K\beta$ XES difference signal that cannot be ascribed purely to a spin variation.

For $K\alpha$, the smaller spectral differences and the strong influence of interactions other than the $2p\text{-}3d$ exchange, that we are currently not able to disentangle, call for caution when these lines are used to obtain spin information. The $K\alpha$ lines may still be a good choice for experiments where the ligand environment changes only very little, such as in pump-and-probe experiments and *in situ* studies (catalysis, batteries, fuel cells ...).

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Additional experimental details, multiplet calculations of XES spectra, experimental $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ XES spectra of Fe^{3+} and mixed-valence samples, $K\beta\text{-IAD}$, $K\alpha_1\text{-FWHM}$ and $K\alpha\text{-IAD}$ parameters vs nominal spin, COG of the $K\beta$ and $K\alpha$ XES spectra as a function of average ligand electronegativity, $K\beta\text{-IAD}$

IAD values after COG alignment, Fe²⁺ HS and LS electronic configurations in a configuration interaction picture, comparison of spectra of the more metallic compounds and between octahedral and tetrahedral local coordination, K $\beta_{1,3}$ -M₁ vs oxidation state, additional K β and K α XES difference signals, multiplet calculations of XES differences, and XAS spectra of all the measured samples. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Synopsis: The lineshapes of the K β XES difference signal between Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ species of fluorides and water solutions reveal a different origin. The typical shape with two features of opposite sign in agreement with a decrease in the exchange splitting and hence of spin is obtained for the solid-state fluoride samples. For the water solutions, the two features having the same sign indicate an origin beyond a spin variation.